

ONLINE APPENDIX TO THE COMPLETED RESEARCH PAPER “UNPACKING THE ROLE OF INDIVIDUALS IN PROCESS MINING: A LITERATURE REVIEW AND RESEARCH FRAMEWORK”

Online Appendix of a Completed Research Paper

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Abstract

This is the online appendix of the completed research paper “Unpacking the Role of Individuals in Process Mining: A Literature Review and Research Framework” at the Thirty-Fourth European Conference on Information Systems, 2026. This online appendix contains the data structures (Gioia et al., 2013) showcasing our coding procedure. We provide samples of the first-order concepts that were used to construct second-order themes and subsequently the aggregate dimensions. To ensure a better overview, we split the data structure for each aggregate dimension.

Appendix A: Contingency factors

Figure 1. Data structure for the aggregate dimension “Technical level”

Figure 2. Data structure for the aggregate dimension “Individual level”

Figure 3. Data structure for the aggregate dimension “Organizational level”

Appendix B: Individuals in Process Mining

Figure 4. Data structure for the aggregate dimension “Behavior”

Figure 5. Data structure for the aggregate dimension “Usage patterns”

Figure 6. Data structure for the aggregate dimension “Affect”

Appendix C: Value

Figure 7. Data structure for the aggregate dimension “Value”

References

- Gioia, D. A., Corley, K. G., & Hamilton, A. L. (2013). Seeking Qualitative Rigor in Inductive Research: Notes on the Gioia Methodology. *Organizational Research Methods*, 16(1), 15–31.